

COMMUNICATIVE PRACTICES IN A POLY CULTURAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The relevance of the problem is that intercultural communication in a polycultural environment has its peculiarities. It involves people from reference cultures that are quite different in perception. To achieve effective communication some contextual barriers should be overcome.

The concept of intercultural communication started to develop in the 1990s in Russia and originally was connected with a new paradigm in foreign languages training. Effective intercultural communication should have linguistic and cultural skills. R.D. Lewis says that we should learn languages in a close connection with the studies of cultures and adds that '... while learning other languages, especially those containing different ideas, you can enlarge your experience of the other cultures and get a deeper understanding of the nature of things'. We assume that the universities of the 21st century have sufficient resources to conduct training sessions for students of different cultures and languages. So, we should develop appropriate methods and programs.

The purpose of the study is to justify the choice of communicative practices in the sphere of intercultural communication in an educational environment theoretically. The methods are the study, questionnaire, analysis and implementation of modern techniques of the educational process. The results of the research can be applied in the theory and practice of a foreign language training, intercultural communication.

Keywords: interlanguage communication, intercultural differences, polycultural environment, communication efficiency, foreign languages, English.

1. INTRODUCTION

The notion of intercultural communication being primarily used in business and production is an integral part of the society nowadays. Its aim remained the same: to provide intercultural communication and understanding between partners (Donets, 2001). Intercultural communication as a scientific issue has been widely discussed in a world science. It is mostly based on the researches of the 20th century in the areas of linguistic structuralism, hermeneutics, a theory of social information (Hall, 1959). In Russia the start of intercultural communication can be referred to the mid-1990s. It was stated that in order to establish proper

intercultural contacts we should possess both cultural and language skills. One of the tendencies of linguistics nowadays is to draw a parallel between language and culture as two sides of spiritual culture of a nation (Dooly, 2015). This approach involves the study of the country's history, standards of behaviour, sociolinguistics and other related fields of knowledge (Leaver, 2020). Besides the approach to intercultural communication provides an opportunity to look at world events from a different perspective. This helps to develop respect and tolerance for people from other cultures. Higher School of Foreign Languages and Translation of Kazan Federal University was chosen as a platform for research in our study. We know that universities are places where educational, orientational, moral, ethical, cultural and environmental functions are carried out (Sabirova, Khanipova, Latypov, 2018). Moreover they play an important role in solving different complex problems (Rakhimbirdieva, Khaimova, Kurmaeva, 2018).

2. PURPOSE AND METHODS

The purpose of the research work can be defined as assessment of the role of the university in promoting intercultural communication. The tasks are: 1) to obtain data for a conceptual model of intercultural communication training; 2) to provide the methodological support of the training process.

In this research the following methods were used: 1) study and analysis of scientific literature on the issue under study; 2) questioning and interviewing; 3) method of statistical analysis.

3. RESULTS

The experiment that we carried out consisted of three steps.

The first step. The most important point here is that the experimental ground is the university that is situated in the Republic of Tatarstan, Russia. Tatarstan was not chosen at random. We believe that the results of the experiment would be more interesting if conducted in a multinational republic. We should take this fact into account so it can influence the results of the study.

We have conducted the study to find out the degree of intercultural development among university students of different courses. The age of the respondents varied from 17 to 22. Both genders took part in the experiment. We believe that the gender aspect is an extremely important in modeling intercultural communication training programs. The structure of the questionnaire consists of 2 steps. At first we asked the students questions concerning the most probable challenges in the process of intercultural communication. At second, we assessed the answers by the ranking method. The structure of the questionnaire was meant to develop a conceptual model of intercultural training programs. The questionnaire included six blocks, which contained information about a student, communication process with representatives of other nations, students' interest in the communication process, peculiarities of communication environment, factors influencing communication process, information environment. See the questions of the questionnaire in Table 1:

Table 1

Blocks and questions	Why is the question asked
A. Information about yourself:	
1. Gender	The question considers a gender approach. It takes into account interests of both genders. This approach can help to implement, monitor and evaluate activities and to make training programs so that both genders can benefit equally.
2. Age	Here we apply an age-based approach which should be taken into account in a process of modeling a framework of intercultural communication.
3. Education	Here we apply a flexible approach to training programs, focusing on different levels of students' performance.

B. Can you communicate with representatives of other peoples	It provides an opportunity to identify barriers in communication
What difficulties may arise during communication process: barrier of mutual misunderstanding, stylistic barrier, psychological barrier, authority barrier, relationship barrier	It identifies the barriers in the communication process and work out the rules to overcome them in a training program
C. Ways to enhance interest in intercultural communication	It develops topics of the training program. It gives recommendations of particular practical skills that are necessary for an effective communicative process.
D. Communication environment (social networks, Skype, direct communication, hobby clubs, forums, blogs, dating sites, subcultures)	It defines more comfortable environment for the user. The university should ensure interactive communication by applying the technologies that respondents have chosen. Hobby groups and subcultures deserve special attention.
E. Openness in communication	It gives the recommendations how to make training programs in accordance with ethical norms, etiquette, tolerance and the principles of interpersonal communication
1. What do you do in order to express yourself in a communication process or how to place a person?	
2. What prevents you from expressing yourself in a live direct communication (books, television, Internet, self-confidence)?	
F. International Library and Information Environment	It takes into account possibility of access to library's international full-text resources (electronic and traditional) from mobile devices. It discusses the question of possible use of 'a live book' in foreign languages in a training process. It identifies the preferable type of mobile device.
1. What types of literature do you prefer in the international collection of the University Library (popular science, references, documentary, fiction, memoirs, educational literature, technical literature)?	
2. What source of information do you prefer to take the information from (audiobook, electronic book, printed book)?	
3. Which mobile device do you use when you read an e-book (digital book, reader, netbook, laptop, tablet, iPhone).	

4. SUMMARY

Interpretation of the results of the questionnaire. We can draw the following conclusions:

1. Readiness to communicate with people of different cultures

The answer 'Insecurity' was the most popular one when asked about difficulties in communication process among boys and girls of all age groups. The answer 'Suspicion' was the least popular. The most common answer to the question about mutual misunderstanding was 'Unclear, indistinct' both among boys and girls. The answer 'He/she uses a large number of expletives' was mentioned least by respondents.

2. Ways to enhance interest in intercultural communication

Developing tolerance and communicative skills was the most common answer. The least number of respondents would like to adapt to new living conditions.

3. Communication environment

All respondents proved to be active in virtual space, they preferred social networks and dating sites. Furthermore, it is very important for them to communicate directly.

4. Openness in communication

In communication process all respondents use smiles and express admiration, listen and speak on topics close and interesting to their interlocutors. The main obstacle that prevents the respondents from live communication was the Internet. It was the most common answer.

5. Multinational literature and information environment

All respondents believe that information sources in foreign languages should be more useful in the training process. All genres are equally important: popular science, documentary, memoir, educational, technical and fiction literature.

Printed books occupied the first place in the answers of students of both genders. When reading an e-book as a mobile device, the respondents used most often a tablet and a laptop.

6. The way to get close to the culture of a different country

All the respondents gave a unanimous answer to this question. In order to get close to the culture of a different country, it is necessary to communicate with a representative of this culture.

In this paper we examined the theoretical and practical issues of intercultural training that can be used in the multicultural environment of the university. This approach to the process of intercultural communication training seems reasonable to us. It allows both to differentiate between universal and national issues, to integrate them in the process of planning and implementing the course of training.

In this regard the urgent problem is the formation of intercultural communication that allows an individual (student) to find that a different culture is not so different from his own culture. Moreover, it is vital to find issues that brings them together and unites them. This process is possible in case the communicants learn to interpret everything that happens in the process of intercultural communication from the perspective of a different culture. They should learn to correlate existing stereotypes with their personal experience and draw adequate conclusions. All of this will help to comprehend someone else's reality by revising their views and ideas about a different culture. It is extremely important to be able to solve conflict situations in the process of intercultural communication and to correctly navigate it in a united cultural space.

5. CONCLUSION

In the Russian communicative theory works by N.K. Ikonnikova, T.G. Grushevitsky, V.D. Popkov, A.P. Sadokhin, O.A. Leontovich, I.A. Malkovsky, S.G. Ter-Minasova can be mentioned. Nowadays an academic subject "Intercultural communication" is actively studied in research centers and higher educational institutions in Russia. However, the researcher O.A. Leontovitch states that the intercultural communicative researches need clarification and common methodological principles and conceptual approaches (Leontovich, 2002). According to O.A. Leontovich, in Russia such interdisciplinary areas as linguistic and regional studies, ethnolinguistics, ethnopsycholinguistics, linguosociopsychology and linguoculturology are being studied more thoroughly (Fayzullina, 2019). It should be noted that a greater emphasis on linguistics and applied sociolinguistics is a hallmark of intercultural communication. The fact why we observe the lack of a unified theoretical approach to the study of intercultural communication in Russia can be explained in the following way. We attach a different meaning to the term intercultural communication of this sphere in Russian and English science. The term 'intercultural communication' is mostly used in the meaning of the interaction of two participants who belong to different cultures. Research papers define it as the exchange of knowledge, ideas and emotions between people of different cultures. Thus, intercultural communication needs to be carefully studied and should overcome various kinds of intercultural discrepancies (Anderson,

(2020).

The issue of intercultural communication is mainly connected with the process of globalization, which is migration process, the expansion of the information and communication space. Globalization is the main driving force of development of intercultural contacts. Due to it new sociocultural entities are being created (Dodd, 1991). Deeper learning of the cultural peculiarities of other countries has become possible since the integration of Russia into global processes has begun. The way to common world space can not be realized without mastering cultural issues and understanding between people of different cultures. Intercultural communication used to be a theoretical not an applied subject, but nowadays it requires a set of skills that can and should be mastered. The skills of intercultural communication is a strict necessity for people whose activities related to the interaction between cultures, for instance, in negotiations, and in situations of social tension. That is why we can notice that a new profession called a specialist in intercultural communication and new forms cross-cultural training have appeared.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper has been supported by the Kazan Federal University Strategic Academic Leadership Program, Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Moscow Pedagogical State University, ANOHE «Moscow International University».

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